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Annotation: *this article presents concepts for the development of marketing strikes of the cultural sphere. The specifics of marketing concepts in organizations of the art and cultural sphere are highlighted. The main focus is on the processes of forming a marketing portfolio based on the requirements and desires of customers.*

Keywords: *marketing, socio-cultural sphere, Concept, Art, Culture, Capital, segmentation, sector, market economy, cultural and spiritual goods, business, intangible.*

From the beginning of the 20th century to the present, the concept of marketing has been seriously changing under the influence of economic, social, technological conditions of management. Initially, companies based their market decisions mainly on profit-making considerations, and then began to realize the strategic importance of meeting customer needs, resulting in the concept of marketing. At the present stage, when making decisions, many companies take into account the interests of society, that is, based on the concept of socially responsible marketing. The general vector of changes in Marketing thinking can be defined as an attempt to understand the importance of the social consequences of commercial activity from maximizing economic interests. The development of the marketing concept in the social sphere is, in fact, an adaptation to the principles of classical marketing, based on the understanding of the environment in which social organizations operate and the specificity of the special mission that they perform in society. Serious advantages for professionals in the social sphere who have adopted the Marketing approach are the presence of a mature theoretical, methodological, instrumental and technological base of classical marketing and many years of experience in its application.

The difficulty lies in the fact that it is not correct to assess the final effectiveness of marketing in the social sphere only in terms of profit and profitability. Therefore, it is necessary to look for new criteria and indicators for assessing such activities for individual institutions and the entire social sphere. An Integral assessment indicator can be the quality (level) of the life of society. Having seen in the marketing of the prism of human needs satisfaction through sharing, we now witness that the real goals of the marketing system reflect four important options: to reach the highest possible level of consumption, to meet the maximum consumer need, to ensure the choice as much as possible and to maximize the quality of life. Maximizing quality of life is a strategic goal of social marketing. From these positions, marketing activities in the social sphere should ensure not only the quantity, quality, variety and availability of services at affordable prices, but also the quality of the cultural and physical environment of people. The main assessment indicator of Marketing activities-efficiency will not be lost, but will have additional values. Economic efficiency, which is a criterion of profit, is complemented by social efficiency, the criterion of which is the increase in human capital and the improvement of living standards due to the full satisfaction of personal, group and social needs.

According to this goal setting and the general definition of marketing as a market management concept, we form the basic principles of marketing in the social sphere:

- directing activities to meet the socially significant needs of society and individuals;

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- use of classic marketing tools to analyze the formation and promotion of consumer demand for technologies, methods and main market participants, services;
- inclusion of moral (humanistic) values in the marketing decision-making process;
- the economic priority of social effectiveness in assessing the effectiveness of marketing activities.

In terms of these principles, marketing is an effective means of achieving socially significant goals based on the satisfaction of social and personal needs. The Ideal desired result is to achieve a balance of the interests of business, state and population.

Together with this, let's dwell on the role of marketing in the activities of the field of culture and art in Uzbekistan today. As a specialist in this field, I can say that it is in today's market conditions that the development of marketing services in the field of culture and art remains an urgent issue. Let's take cultural centers that operate only in districts, cities and villages, it is in them that we can say that the marketing service is not established at all. All cultural centers are funded by the state. Cultural institutions in the United States alone

95 percent are self-molizing, the reason we can say that the marketing service in them is 100 percent established. We can also say with confidence that we will definitely achieve this result if we can correctly implement every principle of marketing. In this regard, we want to point out several proposals for the development of marketing service in cultural centers and the mechanism of their implementation.

Our proposal: currently, 837 cultural centers (13% operate in the vacant rooms of various organizations) have their own building. Organization of modern sound recording, photo and video studios on a private-partnership basis in a cultural center with its own building, "Karaoke", "Book cafe" "aerobics" circle. At the same time, the use of various modern advertising tools under the eyes of the Cultural Center.

Implementation mechanism: development and implementation of a special system for organizing modern sound recording, photo and video studios, Karaoke, Book cafe, aerobics circle, which attracted local budget funds, young entrepreneurs, in order to significantly organize youth leisure activities and increase the extra-budgetary funds of cultural centers. Formation of modern "advertising media " under the Cultural Center and provision of a paid advertising service.

In conclusion, visitors to cultural centers will increase in a significant order, and additional paid receipts will be established. The more paid service services we organize under cultural centers, the more out-of-budget funds the center will receive. Each month, an additional amount is added to the salary of employees. A children's playground will provide a place for recreation for children of residents who are far away.

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